

TEACHERS STRESS AND TYPE OF SCHOOL: IS THERE ANY LINK?

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ABSTRACT

Stress is a non-specific demand on the individual's body or mind to adapt a change physically or psychologically. The term stress is used to describe the feeling of a person who is required to deviate from normal to self-desired functioning in the work place as the result of opportunities, constraints or demands relating to potentially important work related outcomes. The impact of stress in the workplace on the employee's physical health, mental well-being and effectiveness in the workplace has been increasingly recognized in recent years. Stress is an occurrence that must be recognized and addressed in various professions- the teaching profession is no exception. In recent years, inclusive education has risen to prominence, which changed the traditional roles of teachers, from using a "talk and chalk" method, to being more pupil-centered. Research highlights that teacher's experience with respect to inclusive education is very limited, and that they do not have the skill and disposition to handle diversity.

Keywords: Teachers stress, type of school, level of stress, Supervisory support, role stress, role ambiguity, job, stress, life satisfaction, job satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is an occurrence that must be recognized and addressed in various professions- the teaching profession is no exception. In recent years, inclusive education has risen to prominence, which changed the traditional roles of teachers, from using a "talk and chalk" method, to being more pupil-centered. Research highlights that teacher's experience with respect to inclusive education is very limited, and that they do not have the skill and disposition to handle diversity (Engelbrecht & Eloff, 2001).

Anyone who has worked in a helping profession such as teaching will appreciate how stressful such professions can be. Everyday interactions with students can trigger the experience of stress in teachers. The reality is that the teacher is normal but the work situation is often unpredictable and sometimes even abnormal from a professional point of view. Stress at work has been singled out as an important area of investigation for several reasons: most people spend a substantial amount of time at work, and work is important as a fundamental means for implementing and fulfilling personal aspirations and expectations. Practitioners in teaching are normally committed to giving their best for the welfare of those entrusted in their care. While the commitment is laudable, the consequences can be detrimental when the job demands overshadow the individual's coping resources, as well as the job rewards; thus leaving the practitioner feeling unhappy and unable to perform well. Indications are that teacher stress is one of the main forms of professional stress (Federale Onderwysersraad, 1990). By definition, teaching is effective when it enables student learning. But identifying effective teaching is

complicated by the fact that teachers often have very different students. Students start the year with different achievement levels and different needs. Moreover, some teachers tend to get particular types of students year after year (that is, they tend to get higher-performing or lower performing ones). This is why so-called value-added measures attempt to account for differences in the measurable characteristics of a teacher's students, such as prior test scores and poverty (Bill & Melinda Gates 2013). However, teaching is often a stressful occupation, with demands from administrators, colleagues, students, and parents compounded by work overload, shifting policies, and a lack of recognition for accomplishments (Greenglass & Burke, 2003).

DEFINITIONS OF JOB STRESS

Lath (2010) described occupational stress as the physical and emotional response that occurs when workers perceive an imbalance between their work demands and their capability and resource to meet these demands.

Kyriacou (2001) "teacher stress as the experience by a teacher of unpleasant emotions such as tension, frustration, anger and depression resulting from aspects of his work as a teacher."

According to European Commission, Directorate General for Employment and Social Affairs, (2005) "The emotional cognitive, behavioral and physiological reaction to aversive and noxious aspects of work, work environments and work organizations. It is a state characterized by high levels of arousal and distress and often by feelings of not coping."

IMPACT OF TEACHERS STRESS IN THE PRESENT SITUATION IN INDIA

Continuous stress leads to strain which in turn make the individual to burnout in their workplace which further brings in job dissatisfaction. Occupational stress is defined in different ways over the years. In the Guidance on Work-related Stress issued by the European Commission in 2002, work-related stress is defined as 'a pattern of emotional, cognitive, behavioural and physiological reactions to adverse and noxious aspects of work content, work organisation and work environment ; the main emphasis is on the workplace as the source of stress. Thus, by considering the purpose of the present study, the investigators refers school teachers occupational stress as a negative emotional state experienced by them out of challenged turnover intension and organisational climate, teachers effectiveness and Demands at work, Work family conflict and family work conflict, Supervisory Support, Role Ambiguity, Role Stress, Organizational Management, Job satisfaction, Life Satisfaction, Task Stress existing in the present school.

TYPES OF STRESS

Dr Karl Albrecht, a management consultant and conference speaker based in California, is a pioneer in the development of stress-reduction training for businesspeople. He defined four common types of stress in his 1979 book, "Stress and the Manager."

Albrecht's four common types of stress are:

- i. Time stress.
- ii. Anticipatory stress.
- iii. Situational stress.
- iv. Encounter stress.

1.3.1. Time Stress

When the individual experience time stress he worry about time, or the lack thereof. The person worries about the number of things that he has to do, and he has the fear that he will fail to achieve something important. He may feel trapped, unhappy, or even hopeless. Common examples of time stress include worrying about deadlines or rushing to avoid being late for a meeting.

1.3.2. Anticipatory Stress

Anticipatory stress describes stress that one's experience about concerning the future. Sometimes this stress can be focused on a specific event, such as an upcoming presentation that he is going to give. However, anticipatory stress can also be vague and undefined, such as an overall sense of dread about the future, or a worry that "something will go wrong."

1.3.3. Situational Stress

The human being experience situational stress when the person in a scary situation that he has no way to control over. This could be an emergency. More commonly, however, it's a situation that involves conflict, or a loss of status or acceptance in the eyes of their group. For instance, getting laid off or making a major mistake in front of their team are examples of events that can cause situational stress.

1.3.4. Encounter Stress

Encounter stress revolves around people. The individual experience encounter stress when he worry about interacting with a certain person or group of people the person may not like them, or he might think that they're unpredictable. Encounter stress can also occur if his role involves a lot of personal interactions with customers or clients, especially if those groups are in distress. For instance, physicians and social workers have high rates of encounter stress, because the people they work with routinely don't feel well, or are deeply upset. This type of stress also occurs from "contact overload": when the person feel overwhelmed or drained from interacting with too many people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Okeke (2013) this study employed the descriptive-correlation research design to determine whether secondary school teachers experience work-related stress. Participants included 239 teachers selected from schools in the Hhohho region of Swaziland. A questionnaire was used as the instrument to determine the level of work-related stress experienced by these teachers. Findings showed that teachers were moderately stressed by their work. Contractual problems and the nature of their work were two aspects that were reported to be the main stressors for the sample, while the work environment and work relationships were only mildly stressful. There was a weak relationship between the level of work-related stress and the demographic variables of gender, marital status, and qualifications. Age had a moderate significant relationship with the level of work-related stress for the sample. The study recommends that stress management programmes for teachers are imperative to deal with the consequences of stress.

Rabindra Kayastha et al (2012) conducted a study to compare the occupational stress of the relationship between three different types of schools that is government, public, and private schools with particular reference to corporate, Higher Secondary Level School of Nepal. 268 teachers with at least one year experience in anyone of three different types of schools in Nepal were selected for this study. The sample was selected randomly, each from government, public, and private schools. The following criterion measures chosen for testing the hypotheses in the study, occupational stress was measured by occupational stress index by Srivastava and Singh (1981). The data was collected by research assistants through direct contact with the respondents. Findings reveal that there is no significant difference in occupational stress among Higher Secondary Level School Teachers of Nepal in three different types of schools as the obtained p value 0.499. Insignificant relationship was found in comparison of three different types of schools in Nepal.

Ms.Rashmi Ram Hunnur(2013) noted that teacher stress on the other hand experiences in teachers of unpleasant, negative emotions, such as anger, frustration, anxiety, depression and nervousness, resulting from some aspect of their work as teachers. Teachers nowadays have to deal with so many different demands and pressures, emotional, physical, and administrative and management duties but also to some inconsiderate parents' demands and wants. Besides that, the large number of students in a classroom, packed timetable, uneven duties, uncomfortable working conditions, co-curriculum activities, meetings, in-house trainings, courses to attend extra classes and the unnecessary amounted paperwork are some of the main contributions to the increased causes of stress among teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To measure the level of job stress among school teachers
- To compare the level of job stress among Public and private school teachers

ANALYSIS

Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and type of school

Stress level	Type of school			Total	Value	P-value
	Public	Private Aided	Private Un-aided			
Medium	155	23	47	225	1.163	.000
High	23	40	102	165		
Total	178	63	149	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and type of school.

Chi-Square test is carried out to find out the association between level of stress and type of school. The chi-square test results shows that out of 178 public school respondents 155 of them having medium level of stress, and 23 of them having high level of stress. 23 of the respondents from private Un-aided school having medium level of stress, and 40 of them having high level of stress out of 63 respondents. Out of 149 respondents, 102 of them having high level of stress and 47 of respondents having medium level of stress. Totally 165 of the respondents having high level of stress. The chi-square value is 1.163 with respective p-value 0.00 so there is statistical association between the level of stress and type of school, so the Null Hypothesis is rejected and Alternative Hypothesis is accepted. Early studies by Jeffrey (2008) indicating that private school students outperformed public school students, even controlling for socioeconomic status, could never quite shake the suspicion that families aggressive enough to pursue a private option had something different about them in terms of motivation and support—suggesting that the teachers and family might have been more responsible than the school for the students’ academic success.

Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and Age

Stress level	Age						Total	Value	P-value
	< 25	26-30	31-35	36-40	41-45	>45			
Medium	17	0	111	0	88	9	225	1.363	.000
High	18	24	80	17	0	26	165		
Total	35	24	191	17	88	35	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and Age

The association between the level of stress and age is find out with the help of chi-square test. Here 80 respondents of the respondents in the age group 31-35 reported with high level stress and 111 respondents reported with medium level of stress. The 35 respondents having more than 45 years of age out of that 35 26 of them having high level of stress and 9 of them having medium level of stress. There are 24 respondents in the age group of 26-30 all of them avail high level of stress. Totally 225 respondents having medium level stress, 165 respondents having high level stress. The result supported by Jaita Mondal (2011) according to his study was found that the teachers of >25 to <=35 years of age were less satisfied in Job Role item than the other two groups. From this finding it can said that the age has a significant role on the job stress and job satisfaction. The mid age teachers were having more stress and less satisfaction, might be because these age people were ambitious and building their career. This time they need more support from the management. The present study the chi-square value is 1.363 with respective p-value 0.00 so there is significant statistical association between the level of stress and age, so the Null Hypothesis is rejected and Alternative Hypothesis is accepted.

Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and Marital Status

Stress level	Marital Status		Total	Value	P-value
	married	single			
Medium	208	17	225	1.311	.252
High	147	18	165		
Total	355	35	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and Marital Status.

Chi square test has been conducted to find out the association between level of stress and marital status of respondents. Here out of 355 married teachers 208 of them having medium level of stress and 147 are avail with high level of stress. 35 respondents are single out of that 17 reported with medium level of stress and 18 of them reported high level of stress. Totally 225 respondents having medium level stress, 165 respondents having high level stress. The chi-square result value is 1.311 and the significance value with 0.252 is that is $>$ than 0.05 so there is no association between the level of stress and marital status. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. Also, no significant associations between the occupational stress of teachers and marital status are presented in this study, and this finding is in accord with results of Al-Qaryoti (2006)

Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and Gender

Stress level	Gender		Total	Value	P-value
	male	female			
Medium	68	157	225	5.617	.018
High	69	96	165		
Total	137	253	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and years of Gender

The association between the level of stress and gender is find out with the help of chi-square test. From the table it is inferred that male respondents available are 137 out of that 68 of them having medium level of stress and 69 of them having high level of stress, there are 253 female respondents available out of that 157 of them inferred with medium level stress, and 96 of them having high level of stress. Female respondents having high level of stress than the male respondents , this may be due to taking care of family and the work simultaneously by the female respondents , totally 225 respondents having medium level stress, 165 respondents having high level stress. The results supported by Aqsa (2011), in his the previous study female faculty members experience more stress as compared to male faculty members. The reason behind females experiencing more stress is embedded in Pakistani cultural settings. In Pakistan, there is generally high pressure exerted on females to maintain balance between job & family demands, moreover, working in a male dominated society is another cause of experiencing more stress as compared to male faculty members.

Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and Education

Stress level	Education			Total	Value	P-value
	UG	PG	professional degree			
Medium	0	26	199	225	1.334	.000
High	46	62	57	165		
Total	46	88	256	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and Education.

The association between the level of stress and education of respondents has been find out by the chi-square test. From the table it inferred that all the 46 under graduate respondents having high level of stress. 26 post graduate respondents having medium level of stress and 62 post graduate respondents reports with high level of stress, out of 256 professional degree respondents 199 of them avail with medium level of stress and 57 of them having high level of stress. Totally 225 respondents having medium level stress, 165 respondents having high level stress. The results shows that all the under graduate respondents reports about high level stress, and out of 88 post graduate respondents 62 reports high level stress, the chi-square value is 1.334 with the corresponding p-value 0.00 denotes that there is a statistical significance between the level of stress and education of respondents. Jaita (2011) By analyzing the role of education level on Job satisfaction and Job stress of the teachers, it was found that the teachers having postgraduate degree were having more job stress than the Undergraduate The teachers having postgraduate degree were having less Job satisfaction than the Undergraduate and Graduate teachers.

Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and Family Type

Stress level	Family Type		Total	Value	P-value
	joint	nuclear			
Medium	43	182	225	48.407	.000
High	87	78	165		
Total	130	260	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and Family Type.

To find out the relationship between the level of stress and family type the chi-square test has been carried out. 130 respondents are in joint family out of that 87 of them having high level stress and 43 of them having medium level stress. 260 Nuclear family respondents available and 78 of them reported with high level stress and 182 respondents having medium level stress. Totally 225 respondents having medium level stress, 165 respondents having high level stress. Chi –square value 48.407 and the p-value is 0.00 so the results statistically significance with each other, hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. A Study of Seema Pervez (2003) also supported this result that is in his study he fined out that there is significance difference for teachers from joint and nuclear family system, he indicates that teachers from joint families show high level of stress than teachers from nuclear families.

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE RESULTS FOR TYPE OF SCHOOL AND TEACHER STRESS

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	F	P - value
Supervisory Support	Government	178	17.4775	3.67340	.27533	22.447	.000
	Private Aided	63	21.6032	6.84515	.86241		
	Private Un-Aided	149	19.1745	3.52353	.28866		
	Total	390	18.7923	4.52306	.22903		
Role Ambiguity	Public	178	5.9607	1.66167	.12455	15.363	.000
	Private Aided	63	6.9048	2.54453	.32058		
	Private Un-Aided	149	7.0067	1.58752	.13005		
	Total	390	6.5128	1.87216	.09480		
Role Stress	Public	178	17.8202	4.78005	.35828	4.305	.014
	Private Aided	63	17.9365	4.80213	.60501		
	Private Un-Aided	149	19.0134	1.00664	.08247		
	Total	390	18.2949	3.84437	.19467		

Organisational Management	Public	178	14.9888	3.13715	.23514	36.466	.000
	Private Aided	63	17.6508	4.84654	.61061		
	Private Un-Aided	149	18.2013	3.33487	.27320		
	Total	390	16.6462	3.84707	.19480		
Job Satisfaction	Public	178	14.8933	3.01313	.22584	129.171	.000
	Private Aided	63	19.2540	4.51152	.56840		
	Private Un-Aided	149	19.6510	1.33014	.10897		
	Total	390	17.4154	3.66345	.18551		
Life Satisfaction	Public	178	13.8483	3.60548	.27024	61.175	.000
	Private Aided	63	18.5714	4.99262	.62901		
	Private Un-Aided	149	17.3423	2.49803	.20465		
	Total	390	15.9462	4.01727	.20342		
Task Stress	Public	178	12.6742	4.06800	.30491	69.636	.000
	Private Aided	63	18.3492	4.56550	.57520		
	Private Un-Aided	149	15.9060	2.21281	.18128		
	Total	390	14.8256	4.15823	.21056		

To find out the relationship between the independent variable type of school and the dimensions of the dependent variable Teacher stress the one way ANOVA was carried-out. While taking a look with the mean value private unaided school category has the highest among the dimensions Role Ambiguity, Role Stress, Organisational Management, and Job Satisfaction. It is found that the teachers of private un-aided schools express that they have been victims of high level of occupational stress. The study by Jayaraj (2013) reveals the two cadres of higher secondary school teachers a high percentage of the un-aided school teachers compared to government teachers felt that the occupational stress level is high. It is perceived that, lack of interaction, time pressure for completing the syllabus, social status, heavy work load, poor working conditions, sufficient and mutual co operations are the major sources of occupational stress. The present study's other two dimensions of teacher stress mean values are higher for the respondents from private aided schools. And further observed that the F values and their corresponding p-values inferred that all the teachers stress dimensions has the significance, and the respondents opinion differ regarding the type of school where they are from.

FINDINGS

- Out of 390 respondents, 225 have medium level of stress, 165 have high level of stress and no one has low level of stress.
- There is significant association between level of stress and type of school.
- There is significant association between level of stress and designation, years of experience, years of experience until retirement, age, gender, education, family type, number of family members, income and spouse employment.
- There is no significant association between level of stress and marital status.
- Teachers of private un-aided schools have been victims of high level of occupational stress.
- Teachers stress dimensions has the significance, and the respondents opinion differ regarding the type of school where they are from.

SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

The study can be concluded that the teachers from private un-aided school having high level of stress, than public and private aided schools, so the private un-aided school management have to concentrate on their teachers well being, and provided them the job security and has to implement the strategies to avoid the conflict between the teachers in their teaching profession. And the work load of

the teachers also to be consider by the way of qualification and eligibility and willingness of the concern teacher. By the way of taking care of teachers wellbeing the management can reduce the teacher stress, and can promote the student wellbeing indirectly.

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